

Bitcoin Intrinsic Value Cost of Energy: Defining Bitcoin's Value Through Energy Costs

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Abstract

Bitcoin, as the pioneer of decentralized digital currencies, has often presented valuation challenges within the financial ecosystem. Traditional financial instruments and valuation methodologies fall short when trying to pinpoint Bitcoin's intrinsic value. This paper proposes a fresh perspective by considering the substantial energy consumption involved in Bitcoin mining. The Bitcoin Intrinsic Value Cost of Energy (hereinafter referred to as BIVCOE) offers a potential intrinsic value based on this energy expenditure, providing a tangible metric in the otherwise abstract valuation landscape of cryptocurrencies.

1 Background

Bitcoin's mining mechanism relies on a proof-of-work algorithm, which inherently consumes a vast amount of energy. This energy consumption has environmental, economic, and, as we propose, intrinsic value implications for the currency.

2 Objective

To devise a metric, the BIVCOE, which captures an energy-based intrinsic value for Bitcoin. This value can act as a baseline to compare against its volatile market value, assisting investors and analysts in understanding market conditions.

3 Methodology

The BIVCOE model grounds Bitcoin’s intrinsic value on the energy consumed for its production, offering a measure that might help in determining overvaluation or undervaluation relative to the market price.

4 Data source

The primary data for this study is collected from the following sources:

- **Monthly TWh:** Represents the monthly total amount of terawatt-hours utilized in Bitcoin mining. This data is sourced from the energy consumption index created by the University of Cambridge.
- **Circulation Data:** A monthly record of the total number of Bitcoins in circulation.

5 Calculating BIVCOE

5.1 Cost of Used Energy

The financial cost corresponding to the energy consumed for Bitcoin mining is calculated using:

$$\text{Cost}_{\text{Used Energy}}(\text{USD}) = \text{Monthly TWh} \times \text{Average Cost per TWh}(\text{USD})$$

The cost per TWh is considered a constant based on the average worldwide electricity prices. This constant pricing methodology is drawn from the comprehensive study and methodologies employed by the University of Cambridge’s Center for Alternative Finance.

5.2 Minted Bitcoins Calculation

The amount of Bitcoin minted in a given month is the difference between the circulation at the end of the current month and the previous month.

$$\text{Minted}_{\text{Bitcoin}}(\text{BTC}) = \text{Circulation}_{\text{End of Month}}(\text{BTC}) - \text{Circulation}_{\text{End of Previous Month}}(\text{BTC})$$

5.3 BIVCOE Calculation

Using the above data, BIVCOE for a given month is:

$$\text{BIVCOE} = \frac{\text{Cost}_{\text{Used Energy}}(\text{USD})}{\text{Minted}_{\text{Bitcoins}}(\text{BTC})}$$

6 Valuation Spread

To assess the extent to which Bitcoin is overvalued or undervalued at any given point in relation to its intrinsic energy value, we define the Valuation Spread:

$$\text{Valuation Spread (\%)} = \frac{\text{BIVCOE} - \text{Market Price}}{\text{BIVCOE}} \times 100$$

7 Data Visualization

Applying the BIVCOE model to historical data from 2014 to 2023 provides an interesting perspective on Bitcoin's intrinsic value dynamics. Notably, the valuation spread can serve as a significant indicator for potential market adjustments.

Visual representation is crucial for understanding the practical implications of any data-driven analysis. In this section, we'll discuss the two main charts created from our dataset.

7.1 BIVCOE vs. Market Price Chart

This chart showcases the historical relationship between BIVCOE and the market price of Bitcoin. By plotting these two metrics side by side for each month, we can discern patterns and discrepancies between the intrinsic energy value of Bitcoin (as given by BIVCOE) and its actual market price.

Such a visualization allows for quick identification of periods where the market price significantly deviates from its energy-backed valuation, either undervaluing or overvaluing Bitcoin in terms of energy consumption.

7.2 Market Price and Valuation Spread

In the second chart, we juxtapose the market price of Bitcoin with its valuation spread percentage.

This representation highlights periods when Bitcoin’s market price was notably overvalued or undervalued based on its BIVCOE. A positive spread indicates that Bitcoin was undervalued (its market price was below its energy value), while a negative spread shows overvaluation. Through these visualizations, we gain a clearer and more intuitive understanding of Bitcoin’s valuation in terms of its energy consumption, enhancing the insights derived from raw numbers and percentages.

8 Discussion

Our data distinctly indicates that, historically, Bitcoin’s market price has never dropped below its BIVCOE from 2014 to 2023. This consistent trend suggests that energy costs provide a foundational valuation floor for Bitcoin. It might be inferred that market participants implicitly recognize the tangible value imbued by energy expenditure.

However, while historical trends do not show the market price falling below the BIVCOE, this doesn’t preclude such a scenario in future market conditions. Market sentiment, regulatory shifts, and technological advancements in mining efficiency could all play roles in influencing future dynamics.

9 Implications and Further Research

The BIVCOE model provides a tangible metric for investors seeking a foundational valuation of Bitcoin. By understanding the intrinsic energy-based value, market participants can make more informed decisions, especially during extreme market sentiment swings.

Future research could delve deeper into the nuances of regional energy costs, the environmental impact of Bitcoin mining, and the potential influence of renewable energy sources on BIVCOE.

10 Conclusion

The BIVCOE methodology offers a fresh perspective on Bitcoin's valuation, grounding it in the tangible metric of energy consumption. As the world of cryptocurrencies continues to evolve, such tangible valuation models will become increasingly pertinent in navigating the complex financial landscape of digital assets.

11 Sources

Cambridge Bitcoin Electricity Consumption Index: <https://ccaf.io/cbnsi/cbeci/methodology>